

Zybertsphere

Four Cosmological Reference Parameters were identified and values derived from analyses based on the best recent data available for the Mercury precession and the Galileo 1 flyby velocity gain anomalies and from experimental measurements of H_0 , as being, $\mathbb{Z}Z=64324$, $\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}=1.634E-6$, $\mathbb{Z}A'=7.4426E-18$ and $\mathbb{Z}\rho=2\pm 1.5E-26$. As noted elsewhere, $\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}$ is at the low end of estimates but in Zybert Cosmology it is at the high end.

It has been noted that our unique Z_m was still unknown. The next set of simulations of Zybertspheres with $Z_m=0.25E3:512E3$ and $\mathbb{Z}T.N2=E10|\Delta T=E-4$, where Z_a was set to give $\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}=1.634E-6$, would identify which Z_m produced Zybertspheres matching $\mathbb{Z}Z$, $\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}$, $\mathbb{Z}A'$ & $\mathbb{Z}\rho$. For each Z_m , simulations with several Z_a were interpolated to find the Z_a giving $\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}=1.634E-6$. Simulations stopped when $\mathbb{Z}Z=64324\pm 10$ and IC was pre-set to give $\mathbb{Z}A'=7.4426E-18$ and $\mathbb{Z}\rho$ was as determined by the simulations, see Table 1. All data in Table 1 are logarithms of the parameters, with IC = -17.792 for all Z_m .

Table 1. Z_m & Z_a producing $\mathbb{Z}A'=7.4426E-18$ and $\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}=1.634E-6$ when $\mathbb{Z}Z=64324$ (our Zybertsphere)

Z_m	Z_a	$\mathbb{Z}T$	$\mathbb{Z}M$	$\mathbb{Z}R$	$\mathbb{Z}Z$	$\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}$	$\mathbb{Z}A'$	$\mathbb{Z}\rho$	$\Delta\mathbb{Z}A'/\Delta\mathbb{Z}T$	$\Delta\mathbb{Z}Z/\Delta\mathbb{Z}R$	$\Delta\mathbb{Z}A'/\Delta\mathbb{Z}R$
250	26.235	10.59	88	32	4.8083	-5.7866	-17.1277	-25.6092	-27.4208	-27.6106	-49.2448
500	42.245	10.59	96	34	4.8084	-5.7874	-17.1278	-25.6093	-27.4217	-30.0390	-51.6734
1E3	69.560	10.59	106	38	4.8084	-5.7865	-17.1276	-25.6092	-27.4209	-33.3811	-55.0155
2E3	120.005	10.59	115	41	4.8083	-5.7867	-17.1279	-25.6094	-27.4215	-36.4990	-58.1338
4E3	217.605	10.59	122	43	4.8083	-5.7868	-17.1280	-25.6095	-27.4219	-38.8025	-60.4376
8E3	410.355	10.59	126	45	4.8083	-5.7869	-17.1281	-25.6096	-27.4221	-40.2805	-61.9157
16E3	794.400	10.59	129	45	4.8084	-5.7867	-17.1280	-25.6095	-27.4220	-41.1265	-62.7618
32E3	1561.600	10.60	130	46	4.8083	-5.7868	-17.1281	-25.6096	-27.4221	-41.5842	-63.2195
64E3	3095.840	10.60	131	46	4.8084	-5.7866	-17.1280	-25.6095	-27.4219	-41.8164	-63.4516
128E3	6163.020	10.60	131	46	4.8083	-5.7869	-17.1282	-25.6097	-27.4223	-41.9449	-63.5803
256E3	12298.860	10.60	132	46	4.8084	-5.7867	-17.1280	-25.6095	-27.4219	-42.0020	-63.6373
512E3	24587.000	10.59	132	46	4.8083	-5.7864	-17.1280	-25.6095	-27.4216	-41.9944	-63.6296

Amazingly, each Z_m produced Zybertspheres having all four Cosmological Reference Parameters of our visible sphere, when Z_a had a specific value, and which is defined by $Z_a = 0.048 * Z_m + 22.851$ with $R^2=1$ – another Zybert Golden Correlation, specific for our Zybertsphere. Z_m and Z_a are the Zybert Constants in the Zybert Mass Equation which defines all Zybertspheres. As Z_m increases $\mathbb{Z}M$ and $\mathbb{Z}R$ increase but the defining parameters of our Zybertsphere do not change and equal the previously derived values for our visible sphere, and $\Delta\mathbb{Z}Z/\Delta\mathbb{Z}R$ and $\Delta\mathbb{Z}A'/\Delta\mathbb{Z}R$ ($=\Delta\mathbb{Z}Z/\Delta\mathbb{Z}R-21.6349744$) decrease.

Interestingly, each Zybertsphere is $<$ or $\ll E-160$ of its final mass, $\sim E(2 * Z_m)$. And from $Z_m \sim 32E3$, both $\mathbb{Z}M$ and $\mathbb{Z}R$, and $\Delta\mathbb{Z}Z/\Delta\mathbb{Z}R$ and $\Delta\mathbb{Z}A'/\Delta\mathbb{Z}R$, plateau, and limits these parameters above $Z_m \sim 32E3$.

This nature of Zybertspheres is one of many surprising, and probably the most momentous, revelations in Zybert Cosmology. That the Zybert Model of Cosmology identifies this elegant and orderly evolution of Zybertspheres, and which allows fundamental properties of our Zybertsphere to be determined from the rate of Zybert Expansion $\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z}$ ($\Delta\mathbb{Z}Z/\Delta\mathbb{Z}T$) which is measurable. ELT-HIRES and SKA Phase 2 will soon allow the direct detection of the cosmic acceleration. This is yet another fascinating and appealing quality of Zybert Cosmology, reflecting the simple elegant mathematical symmetry of Zybertspheres where most parameters have linear, and the rest non-linear, correlations, and most with $R^2 = 1$ or ≈ 1 . A natural system reflecting such innate mathematical elegance and simplicity.